

An approachment on Tunnel Minimization in Virtual Private Network

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Abstract— A virtual private network is a network object linking two or more private networks that uses public domain infrastructure such as internet to carry traffic between different sites. This paper concentrates upon “Intranet/Extranet “type of VPN, which links an enterprise, headquarters, and remote branches to an internal network over a shared infrastructure to create an IP overlay network by IP Security (IPSec) tunnelling protocol. A tunnel is used to provide connectivity among different networks. This paper proposes an optimal solution to reduce the number of tunnels in VPN while ensuring connectivity and minimized cost of routing.

Keywords— Virtual Private Network (VPN), IP Security, tunneling

I. INTRODUCTION

A Virtual Private Network is a private network established on top of public domain infrastructure like internet to create an overlay network. The service guarantee and security issues in the internet have led many organizations especially corporate networks to shift to VPN. The VPNs are a low cost option and enable long distance connections possible as compared to the traditional leased lines. The VPN makes use of encryption and other security methods to prevent unauthorized users from accessing the network and ensures security and privacy of the data.

Typical applications of VPN include “access VPN” and “Intranet/Extranet VPN” [1]. An access VPN extends almost any type of data (voice, video etc.) to the remote sites. It allows remote corporate users to have a highly secure, customizable access to their corporate intranets via ad hoc tunnels. Intranet/Extranet VPN connects the office headquarter network to the networks of the remote branches and extends the network resources to home offices, business partners, suppliers and customers. This paper concentrates on Intranet/Extranet type of VPN and IPSec [2] is one of the protocols that support Intranet/Extranet type of VPN. It provides encryption/decryption, encapsulation/encapsulation and hashing. A tunnel is a path that forwards the data between two or more VPN endpoints (nodes). There are two approaches for establishing such tunnels: “the CPE-based approach” and “the Network-based approach”. In CPE-based approach, the tunnels are established mainly between the VPN endpoints. These devices are a part of customer’s network and use the core network only for transporting the data over the backbone. Fig 1 shows the VPN based on CPE approach. The main advantage of this approach is its simplicity and it provides the highest level of security over the non-private network as it encrypts/decrypts data at the customer’s site. The major disadvantage of this approach is the cost, complexity and time involved in managing and deploying the network.

In Network-based approach, the core routers are also involved along with VPN endpoints. Fig 2 shows a VPN based on Network-based approach. The advantage of this approach is that it requires less capital expenditure and is more scalable. The primary disadvantage is that this approach has some limitations based on the topology and the services desired.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. Section II discusses the related work and section III discusses the proposed solution. Section IV discusses the simulation results while the section V provides the conclusion and scope for the future work.

Figure 1: CPE-based approach

Figure 2: Network-based approach

II. RELATED WORK

With the increase in demand and usage of VPN, the users of VPN are trying to make it suitable to different demands. A lot of research has been done by different people to optimize the VPN layout by considering different parameters like bandwidth, cost, number of hops, propagation delay, etc.

In paper [1], a new concept of authority to reduce the management complexity of IPsec is discussed. This study has addressed the problem of tunnel minimization in a weighted VPN network layout by formalizing it under three constraints—first on the basis of no constraint, second on the Tunnel Path Length (TPL) which concerns the delay between the VPN endpoints and third on the Tunnel Relay Degree (TRD) which concerns the bandwidth and computing power.

In paper [3], the problem of finding a minimal topology of VPN on the basis of cost is presented. This paper assumes that a tunnel laid over a link has a cost associated with it and considered two parameters: cost of active core nodes and the links over which the tunnels are laid. Two related graph algorithms Minimum Cost (MC) VPN and Minimal Active Set (MAS) VPN are defined and proved to be NP-hard and hard to approximate. The authors have presented two heuristics to solve these problems but both the solutions achieve no strict approximations and are not an efficient solution.

Both the papers [1] and [3] have concentrated on minimizing the VPN topology but have neglected the capacity limitations of the nodes and links.

Paper [4] focuses on network-based VPNs and minimizing the cost of operation of Virtual Private Network that uses the resources of the underlying transport network. The author assumes that the VPN topology i.e. the topology of the ISP and the total cost of underlying link utilization are known parameters. The main

objective of this study is to reduce the cost of operation of ISPs providing network-based VPN services. The model, known as “multicommodity flow problem” (MFC) is deployed in which the bandwidth, reserved over physical connections, for a certain VPN virtual connection, is considered as commodity i.e. individual commodities share common link capacities. Based on the MFC model, a novel routing algorithm called Multicommodity Min-Cost Flow (MMFC) is proposed and proved to be more effective than OSPF routing.

In paper [5], a non-trivial approximation algorithm for the Steiner tree problem and the generalized Steiner network problem on directed graphs is presented. The main objective is finding a minimal tree that constitutes a subset of vertices in a graph and can also make use of the remaining vertices. The NP-Completeness of Steiner Minimal Tree (SMT) is also discussed.

As a solution to the problems in [1] and [3], proposes heuristic algorithms to solve MC-VPN and presents an optimal solution to the problem by reducing the number of tunnels and cost of routing.

III. PROPOSED SOLUTION

This paper proposes a solution that optimizes the Minimum Cost-VPN and gives an efficient algorithm to reduce the number of tunnels considering two parameters: one on the edge cost whenever a tunnel is laid over a link and the cost of core routers which act as endpoints of VPN tunnels. The VPN network is modelled as a directed graph. Each edge (link) of the directed graph is associated with cost. It is assumed that each link has a different cost in every direction. The cost of each link is determined on the basis of bandwidth allocated over that link, for the VPN tunnel. The VPN endpoints are a part of network nodes. The VPN endpoints that connect to the service provider network are called as area border routers and the routers within the service provider network that act as endpoint of tunnels are called as provider edge (core) routers. The main objective is to reduce the number of tunnels without affecting the network connection and to make minimal usage of the resources. Every provider edge node has a weight associated with it. Assuming that the corporate headquarter has got more authority and has most of the servers located there than the branch offices, a logical tree starting at source node (headquarter) and spanning all the remaining border nodes (branch offices) is considered. The main aim is to find a minimal cost directed tree (path) from source to all the destinations while activating only those many core routers that does not cross the given bound.

Mathematically, the problem statement can be formulated as: Given a directed graph $G(V, E)$, where V is the set of vertices and E is the set of edges, an edge weight function L_c , vertex weight function w , a source node $s \in V$, a set of area border nodes $B_a \in V$, considering resource constraints a limit on the number of core nodes to be activated, R , the main aim is to find a set of active paths P_d and a set of active nodes A_c that

$$\text{Minimizes } \sum_{p \in P_d} L_c(e) \dots\dots(1)$$

$$\text{Such that } \sum_{v \in A_c/B_a} w(v) \leq R \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Equation (1) specifies the condition that the cost of the paths p (summation of edges e) that belongs to the active path set P_d is minimized. And equation (2) specifies the condition that the weight of the core routers belonging to the active node set should be less than the given limit R . The proposed solution consists of two phases. First phase involves finding a CPE- based solution for the VPN network i.e. tunnels are established only between the border nodes. The second phase involves application of Network-based approach to the first phase of the solution i.e. activating the provider edge routers that will act as endpoint of tunnels. The algorithm for the CPE-based approach takes the network graph as input, begins from the source node and in each iteration covers one new node from the group of area border nodes until all the nodes from the group

are covered. All the shortest paths found are added to the set of active paths. The border nodes are considered to be always active so they are added to the set of functioning or active nodes. In the Network-based approach, a constant called gain is calculated to select the active core node. The gain gives the cost of the tunnels saved due to activation. The core node with the highest gain is activated and whose weight is within the limit R then it acts as endpoint of the VPN tunnel.

Algorithm 1: CPE-Based approach

- Step 1:** Create two sets- one set contains all the border nodes B_a and the other for the active paths P_d .
Step 2: Find a shortest path from source node to any of the node from the border set and adds the path to the active set path.
Step 3: Make the weights of all the edges along the path covered to zero and remove the covered border node from the set.
Step 4: Repeat the steps [2] and [3] until all the border nodes are covered
Step 5: The shortest paths from source node to all the border nodes belong to the active path set P_d and the border nodes belong to active node set A_c .

Algorithm 2: Network-based approach

- Step 1:** The provider edge (core) nodes with more than one outgoing edges are selected and put in a group, C.
Step 2: The number of outgoing edges for each core node from group C is calculated
 $S \leftarrow$ source node of P_d
 Starting from source node, examine all the nodes with more than one outgoing branch except the border nodes
 No of outgoing edges [tree of P_d] \leftarrow S
Step 3: Calculate a constant called gain for each core node from group C by using the gain formula.

$$\text{Gain} = \frac{(\text{No. of outgoing edges} - 1)}{\sum_{i=s}^t \text{weight}(i,j)}$$

Step 4: Create a group M that contains all the core nodes from C along with their gain value and assign a suitable bound to R.
Step 5: Select the core node with the largest gain from the group M
Step 6: If weight of the selected core node is less than the resource limits R, then activate the core node and reduce the R limit by one.
Step 7: repeat steps [5] and [6] until R is zero and add the activated core nodes to active node set A_c .
 Thus, (P_d, A_c) is the optimal solution.

Fig 3 depicts a VPN state in which source (headquarter) is connected to the destination nodes (branch offices) through the VPN. We consider this VPN example and apply the algorithms to the network graph. Here, $\{s, d1, d2, d3, d4\}$ belong to the group of border nodes and $\{x1, x2, x3, x4, x5\}$ are the core nodes.

In the CPE-based approach, the shortest paths from source to all the destinations are found out. The set of paths constructed in this example are $\{(s, x1, x2, x4, d2), (x4, d3), (x2, x5, d4), (x2, x3, d1)\}$. The VPN tree that is obtained from the set of directed paths after applying CPE-based approach is shown in fig 4. Every edge is used only once as compared to ASP Heuristic in [3] where the edges are used multiple times. In Network-based approach, a directed tree is constructed from the set of directed paths to determine the number of outgoing edges. The core nodes with more than one outgoing edges are selected. Then, gain is calculated to determine which core node to be activated.

Figure 3: A VPN Example

Figure 4: Network after applying CPE-based approach

The gain for the core nodes are: $\{G[x1], G[x3], G[x5]\}=0$, $G[x2]=10$, $G[x4]=6$. We see that $x2$ has the highest gain, so this is the candidate node to be activated. If we assume available resources $R=2$, then we can activate both $x2$ and $x4$. The number of tunnels reduced is 6 out of 12. Fig 5 shows network after activating core nodes. The proposed solution reduces more number of tunnels and takes less computation time compared to the heuristics in [3].

Figure 5: Network after applying Network-based approach

The proposed solution is mathematically evaluated by applying to different network examples by varying the number of border nodes, core nodes and assigning different link weights. The table in fig 6 shows the statistics for different cases.

TABLE 1: Comparison between existing and proposed scheme

Total number of nodes	Total number of tunnels	No of border nodes	No of core nodes	Total number of tunnels remaining after minimization	
				Existing method	Proposed solution
8	10	3	5	4	3
		5	3	7	5
10	12	4	6	9	4
		6	4	9	7
15	18	5	10	12	6
		10	5	14	11
20	27	8	12	17	9
		12	8	19	13

Given a directed graph $G(V,E)$ where V is the vertices and E is the edges, total number of nodes N , total number of tunnels Tn , number of border nodes Bn , number of core nodes Cn , the percentage of tunnels reduced $Tmin$ [3], is given by

$$Tmin = N - \frac{\text{No. of tunnels after minimization}}{N} * 100$$

The same evaluation is done for equal link weights also for varying number of border nodes, core nodes. let Tv represents the number of tunnels remaining after minimization. Based on the mathematical evaluation for equal link weights, Tv is given by

$$Tv = \frac{Tn * \sum_{i=s}^{j=Ba} C(i,j)}{N}$$

Where Tn = tunnels remaining after minimization N = total number of nodes, T = total number of tunnels, $C(i,j)$ = cost of the edges between i (source node) and j (node from border group). If the total number of nodes and tunnels is known then for equal link weights, the above formula for gives an approximate value for the number of tunnels remaining after minimization.

IV.SIMULATION

In this section, the proposed solution is evaluated on random network examples with varying number of nodes and edges. The algorithm is tested on random directed graphs. To avoid complexity, a limit is specified for the number of edges and nodes. The number of nodes is initialised to be in the range of 1 to 50 and the number of edges to be in the range of 10 to 80. The weights of these edges are initialised at random values uniformly distributed between 1 and 11.

On every graph, the algorithm is run on every border router group M size between 2 and 40, including the source node. These groups are selected at random for every graph and every group size from the set of end-user vertices. The weight of border routers is assumed to be equal to 1 for all the nodes. The bound R that specifies the limit on the number of core routers to be made active is between 1 and 20. The results are obtained for over 50 different graphs and the proposed and existing solutions are compared.

There is almost 30-40% increase in the number of tunnels reduced. Also, the proposed solution does uses every edge only once as compared to the existing method which uses edges multiple times thus reducing the time of processing. Fig 6 visualises the result of comparison of number of tunnels reduced for existing and proposed solution.

Figure 6: Tunnels reduced for existing and proposed solution

Figure 7 : Number of tunnels reduced

The simulation is also carried out by varying the number of border nodes and core nodes for different network examples. The number of tunnels reduced is evaluated for two cases- one when the number of border nodes (B_n) is greater than the core nodes (C_n) and the other case when the number of core nodes (C_n) is greater than the number of border nodes (B_n).

It is found that there is almost 40% more reduction in number of tunnels when the number of core nodes is greater than the number of border nodes. Fig 7 visualises the result of comparison of number of tunnels reduced for the two cases.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

The proposed solution addresses the problems in Minimum Cost VPN and provides an optimal performance by reducing even more number of tunnels as compared to existing method. The proposed solution provides almost 30-40% performance improvements. The design uses a combination of CPE-Based and Network-based approach to solve the Minimum Cost VPN problem.

The proposed algorithm can be modified further to reduce even more number of tunnels and applied to situations where weight factor in terms of authority is assigned to the nodes. The problem can otherwise be optimized by considering factors like delay etc.

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